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‘Nature and Dynamics of Health Culture: A Sociological Investigation on Changing Medical Pluralism and Health Seeking Behavior of the Rural Population in the Selected Districts of South Karnataka-India’

Final Synopsis of the Thesis Submitting to Srinivas University, Mangalore for the Award of Doctor of Letters (D.Litt) in Sociology

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CONTENTS

1. Summery	4
2. Statement of the Problem	5
3. Aims and Objectives	6
4. Research Design and Methodology	14-22
5. Significance, Need and Outcome of the Study	23-26
6. Major Findings	26-29
7. Chaptarizations	30
8. List of Publications	33
9. Bibliography	34-39

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1.Summary

Culture creates an inimitable example of beliefs and perceptions as to what “health” or “illness” actually means. In turn, this pattern of beliefs influence how symptoms are recognized, to what they are attributed, and how they are interpreted, and this affects how and when health services are sought. The health seeking behavior of rural populations is very complex because it is influenced by a large number of factors among the most critical of these are issues of awareness.

Studies have suggested that the lack of optimal-utilization of modern health services by rural peoples is due to a variety of socio-cultural reasons. Some services are inappropriately used, whereas others, such as preventive healthcare, are under-utilised due to lack of awareness. Further, overcoming difficulties in communication that prevent one to interact with external changing forces is vital. Despite modern preventive and curative medicine, the healthcare delivery services in several rural areas are still poor and largely unscientific. Within the current comprehensive health intervention services there has been no attempt to understand health culture as a sub-culture complex. But this is precisely the perspective necessary to develop a model of a culturally suited health care delivery system specifically designed for the rural people of the country. Experts have lamented the dearth of micro-level data among such rural populations and have suggested that an effective solution to the health related problems of rural society must situate the problem within the larger contexts of changing health culture. The aim of the current research study is to understand how different forces and approaches to health culture are determined in the larger and changing socio-economic conditions of the rural people. In particular, the study explores the patterns of varying health seeking behavior of rural groups in the selected villages of south Karnataka-India. This study is largely based on geographically and culturally specific data within which to situate a new understanding and interpretations of rural population’s changing health seeking behavior within a context of local socio-cultural norms and aims to reveal how communities’ social and economic resources can be specifically mobilized for remediation campaigns towards improving health status of rural people.

2.Statement of the Problem

Health is one of the vital indicators reflecting the quality of human life. World Health Organization (WHO) describes health as a state of complete physical, mental, social and spiritual well-being and not merely as absence of diseases or infirmity. The plight of rural people has drawn increasing policy attention since 1960. Today the majority of rural people are suffering with various communicable and non communicable diseases. It is stated there is a positive correlation between the health status of rural people and their social, economical and cultural background. Over the last few decades various Indian governments have developed plans to achieve long term goals to provide a comprehensive health care programme for the rural people, and have increasingly emphasized the more immediate need to provide essential basic primary health care and scientific management of rural the rural population's traditional system. Experts have conducted various studies on culturally bounded health behavior among various rural settings. Still, they have not yet completely understood the dynamics of health behavior of rural people. It is found that that poverty, illiteracy, malnutrition, scarcity of potable water , sanitary conditions, poor mother child health services, problems in covering national health and nutritional services, etc. have been found the most vital causative factors for the prevalence of several health issues among rural communities in the country. As far as an organic linkage with the rural health is concerned, there is no basic service for a comprehensive health intervention attempt to understand health culture as a sub culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health care delivery system especially for the rural people of the country. Attempt to comprehend health culture as a sub culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health module programmes specially for the nation's rural people with their different castes and class. Very little work, however, has entailed an in-depth analytical study of comparative emic perspectives of different factors influencing rural people's health behavior in Karnataka-India. This current research has built on recent social science efforts to contribute to filling that gap in the present understanding of impacts of various changing internal and external factors influencing health culture and in shaping health seeking behavior and practicing medical pluralism of rural people in selected villages of Karnataka. Further, this study will help in long term improvements of health behavior of the target population and research findings will certainly help in developing culturally compatible and acceptable developmental intervention strategies at the grass root level for both the Government and NGOs.

3.General Objective:

To study the nature and dynamics of health culture (care practices) and changing health seeking behavior of the rural population and to explore how these are determined by their unique socio cultural background in the selected rural districts of South Karnataka, India

Specific Objectives

1. To study the changing social, economical, cultural, political, health and demographic profile of the studied rural population ;
2. To understand the changing illness ideology of the rural people and to find out the existing perception, health seeking behavior and culturally bounded attitudes about onset of certain common diseases and use of different systems of medicines(Traditional, Ayurvedic, Homeopathy, Allopathic etc) to cure it;
3. To analyze the dimension of rational, non rational, fatalistic and non fatalistic pattern in understanding their behavior for causes and treatment of illness/disease;
4. To reveal the factors accounting for the accessibility to, availability of and affordability for new health care institutions and services and to compare the variability in acceptance of new health schemes on account of rural's unique socio-economic and cultural background;
5. To develop culturally compatible and acceptable new health intervention strategies for the rural community.

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

It is obvious from the objectives of the study presented above that the present sociological study is concerned with the analysis of the rural's health behavior from the different perspectives. A deeper sociological insights into the problem demand much more concentration on the various social issues and the related problems concerning changing the health culture of the rural folk in the recent times. Neither a descriptive nor diagnostic technique was followed. A blend of both diagnostic - exploratory in nature model has been used in this study.

The first step was to select the samples for the actual study. Since the present study was a multi dimensional covering different perspective and the nature of the rural health culture, the number of households having all such characteristic features which fulfills the objectives of the study was quite large. And it was not theoretically possible to cover all these samples in the studied villages. Hence, the Census method of data collection was adopted in this case. Therefore the researcher decided to choose representative samples, having all essential features in a relative proportion. A careful attention was given to an adequacy of the size of the samples for the study.

This entire study has been divided into two parts. First part deals with the demographic aspects like family, size, family income, education, and occupations-etc. The second part deals with subjective issues like the impact of socio economic aspects, concepts, practices, attitudes, perceptions on health and illness, health behaviour, rituals, cultural barriers etc.

A.AREA UNDER STUDY

This study had been conducted in the following Four districts (rural) of Southern Karnataka – India based on the recent RCH and Health and Family welfare survey report

1. Chamrajanagar Districts
2. Hassan Districts
3. Kodagu Districts
4. Kolar Districts

B.SAMPLING DESIGN

Multistage stratified random sampling technique was adopted for the selection of the villages from the Four districts for the current study. In first stage, Four (4) rural blocks were selected from each studied Four rural districts i.e 1 Hassan, 2.Kolar, 3.Chamrajanagar and 4.Kodagu districts on the basis of good, average and poor performance in RCH (Reproductive And Child Health Survey-2010) as per achievement of indicators during the previous assessment year and following discussions with the district health officials. In the second stage, in each district 4 sub-centers (one each from the different PHC jurisdiction areas of the identified blocks) were randomly selected from the each Four blocks. Likewise 16 sub-centers were selected out of the total 93 sub-centers in all Four studied districts of the state.

In the third stage from each of the 16 selected sub-center areas, one sub-center headquarter (HQ) village and one non-HQ village were also randomly selected. Likewise 16

villages comprising 8 HQ and 8 non-HQ were identified out of total 50 villages in the identified sub-center areas from all the Four districts. From the each village a total of 50-60 (depending) household samples have been selected for the current survey. Totally 16 villages, 800 households were selected for the current study. Further Five reputed NGOs working for the rural health care and for the case study purpose 25 local healers were also included based on the purposeful sampling technique for an in-depth study. Few PHCs and sub centers were also consulted.

To successfully address my research objectives I have collected required data from Five sources: **1 .Household Members 2.Other Community Members. 3. NGOs 4 PHCs and the health officials. 5. Traditional Healers.** Although this research was meant to investigate the perspectives of multiple stakeholders, a number of data collection methods were used to generate data directly from the selected samples (households). These efforts had been guided as much as possible by the participatory methodologies developed by an international rural welfare NGOs to eliciting useful data.

Secondary data were collected from the related resources. Further Indices for socio-economic status, environmental status and the health status are constructed according to the general formula used by the United Nations Development Program (UNDP). These indices are used to find the relation between health status and the role, of socio-economic factors. Before the study, an informal consent was taken from the respondents.

C.RESEARCH COMPONENTS

This study used both qualitative and qualitative approaches. Both these methods were useful to find out in depth understanding of the problem and its quantification. Sutton (2006) and others have given a rationale for conducting this kind mixed research. 1. Participant enrichment, 2. Instrument fidelity 3. Treatment integrity and, 4. Significant enhancements.

The methodology had Five major components;

1. Survey;
2. Community Norms Study ;
3. Institutional Ethnography (NGOs /PHCs /Bureaucratic Perspective);
4. Content Analysis ;
5. Case Studies

1.HOUSEHOLD SURVEY

The household survey had been found to be most effective tool for investigating the health phenomenon in all its facets. A survey was conducted among carefully chosen samples of 800 households from the Four districts. This survey had been carried out with the scheduled questionnaires (194) covering the following subject matters (in brief). Respondents were asked to just describe the symptoms in his/her own words (lay perception) and later on classified with the help of a Physician. Here disease/illness had been just used as references for revealing specific health seeking behavior /health care seeking behavior of the respondent's covering---

1 What is health? Reasons for ill health, age, education, income and occupation, caste and its role on health status of a community etc;

2, Cultural concept of health, illness, health behavior, socialization, local healers etc ;

3 Household decision making process on health and illness, common health problems in the area and reasons, cultural perception etc;

5 Mortality, undernourishment, immunizations mental health, western medicine legal provisions, role of PHC, medicalisation health policy and programmes etc .

2. COMMUNITY NORMS STUDY

Part of this study had involved community norms regarding various health issues. Hence, subjects including local community leaders, teachers, advocates, politicians, college students, and other elite's of the society have been interviewed. They have been drawn from the communities –at-large in which studied samples lives. The first session was conducted to elicit community perceptions about health, illness and medical pluralism and opinion about the common health problems according to gender and age. The second part of the community norms study had few discussion sessions to cover the breadth of topics including the relative advantages and disadvantages of various medical systems, medicalisation, rural health problems, cultural barriers, the role of education, Govt. schemes, NGOs role etc. All focus group interviews have been recorded and analyzed using appropriate advanced software's.

3.INSTITUTIONAL ETHNOGRAPHY

This is to understand the rural health scenario from the perspective of local NGOs. This included discussion of organizations philosophy towards rural health, reasons for poor health infrastructure, changing health culture, the structural constraints and success and failure of the

group/s had experienced with its interventions etc. A checklist of around 25 major focus areas of the study problem was prepared after pre-testing the schedule for this purpose.

4. CASE STUDIES

The portion of this component however had consisted of visiting selected 25 local healers to conduct an in-depth interview. Next, I use participant observation technique to better understanding of health practice of the samples/healers. Interviews were semi structured and utilized an interview guide addressing the themes of research objectives.

D. SECONDARY DATA SOURCES

Secondary Data were collected from

1. Records maintained in the village directories;
2. Records maintained by various health agencies;
3. Census records for demographic information;
4. Study reports, articles, books Govt. documents, health survey reports et

E. TOOLS FOR DATA COLLECTION

The following tool were used to collect data

1. Survey;
2. Interview ;
3. Participant observations;
4. Focus group ;
5. Case Study

F. INSTRUMENTS

The following instruments were structured for the collection of both Quantitative and Qualitative data.

1. Respondents (sampling) Level Schedule;
2. Indigenous /local healers Schedule;
3. Community Schedule (focus group);
4. NGO Schedule;
5. Govt. Health Official Schedule

G. RECORDING OF DATA

Data had been recorded using various modern devises

H.ANALYSIS OF DATA

The quantitative data have been analyzed using **Minitab and SPSS** software. The thematically indexed discourse from various interviews, case studies and focus groups had been converted into an extended set of dummy variables and entered into the *minitab* database. It is the most useful because, it would allow the perceptions of the different groups supplying various data (community, household members, NGO staff etc) to be compared to be compared along a spectrum of variables utilizing ANOV method and was tested for the hypotheses related with the research objectives.

The qualitative data generated from the interviews, case studies and focus groups had been thematically coded in the *NUD*IST* database software and had been indexed to identify dominant themes and to link those themes with the specific research questions. The actual data which could not be predicted with certainty include the concept/s of health behaviors, risks involved in health culture, health concept, community perception on various health policies and the programmes implemented by both the Government and NGOs an index tree had been prepared to delineate relationship between themes (Qualitative Research and Solution, 1999).

4.Background and Justification

Culture creates a unique pattern of beliefs and perceptions as to what “health” or “illness” actually mean. In turn, this pattern of beliefs influences how symptoms are documented, to what they are accredited, and how they are interpreted and affects how and when health services are sought. Cultural differences in the recognition and interpretation of symptoms and in the use of health services are the subject of a rich literature. A classic study conducted on the effects of culture on pain: although pain was considered a biological phenomenon, he found that sensitivity to pain and attributing significance to pain symptoms varied by culture and ethnicity. It is said that cultural differences among rural people seeking health care as related to social structures and relationships and the degree of skepticism about professional medical care. Delay in seeking care was found among individuals belonging to cultural groups characterized by ethnic exclusivity, traditional family authority, and high skepticism about medicine. More recently, level of acculturation has been shown to account for differences in the use of health services

within ethnic groups after controlling for age, gender, health status, and insurance coverage.(Anderson,2003)

All rural areas in the Karnataka are unique with extensive geographic and economic variation. When compared to urban populations; however, rural populations are frequently characterized as: being innocent and less educated; living in most remote areas; more likely to be covered by unhygienic environment ; having higher rates of poverty, chronic disease, suicide, deaths from unintentional injuries and motor vehicle accidents; having no or little access to transportation; and having limited economic diversity. All of these issues create challenges and opportunities to improve the health of those living in the rural Karnataka and they play a role in understanding some of the underlying causes associated with issues related to rural health workforce, health services, and special populations.

It is found that majority of these rural believe the causes for ill health are (i) displeasure of supernatural entities, (ii) breach of taboos,(iii) non-fulfillment of obligations towards their gods, (iv) Influence of occultism and (v) Environmental and physical ones. Further, nutritional deficiencies are more in young rural children and reproductive health care is also poor. Health of the rural is prejudiced by a number of factors such as adequate food, housing, sanitation, healthy lifestyles, protection against-environmental hazards and communicable diseases. Experts have indentified variety of issues related to rural's health that is: health culture-including, (1) health, food habits and environment,(2) medicine, health and community-modern, (3) fertility and mortality, (4) interaction of traditional and modern systems of medicine at various levels and (5) reasons for non-adoption of modern practices (Naidu, 2008; Sawin, 1994).

Most of the rural's have high prevalence of many infectious diseases because of their habitation in remote areas. As studied by the most of anthropologists/sociologists and NGOs appear to have a few common practices regarding maternal and child care in rural parts. Among most of the rural's, gastrointestinal disorders, particularly dysentery and parasitic infection are very common leading to morbidity and malnutrition, diarrhoea, dysentery, skin diseases, respiratory diseases have become common because of life style issues. Nutritional problems, anemia due to food taboos, wrong infant feeding practices, fertility, neo-natal

mortality, post-natal mortality, peri-natal mortality, poor life-expectancy etc. are some of the vital health issues being faced by the majority rural people in India (Taywade, 2006).

Socioeconomic status play a vital issue here. Socioeconomic status (SES) underlies three major determinants of health: 1.health care, 2.environmental exposure, and 3.health behavior. In addition, chronic stress associated with lower SES may also increase morbidity and mortality. Reducing socioeconomic status disparities in health will require policy initiatives addressing the components of socioeconomic status (income, education, and occupation etc) as well as the pathways by which these affect health. One can say that today health-seeking behavior of majority rural's is greatly governed by cultural values, beliefs and traditions. Now it is open for gradual change because of different kinds of external interventions. Contrary to changes in health seeking behavior patterns of the rural people, one also can notice tremendous changes, which have occurred with respect to philosophy, knowledge, and practices of indigenous systems such as Ayurveda, Homeopathy, Allopathic, etc. However, it becomes important to work on problems of rural's health because it differs from a particular area to another area owing to their geographical location, historical background and the processes of social change (Bulliyya, 2009). Geographical isolation and limited interactions with other communities has become an obstacle to know the degree of prevalence of HIV/AIDS among rural communities. However in some areas, rurals are emerging as a high-risk group for HIV/AIDS as they migrate driven by displacement or for employment opportunities (Arlappa, 1999; Bose, 2006; Kerketta, 2008). Carstairs (1955) in his study has pointed out that the differences between the points of view of the physicians and the village folk with regard to the theory of etiology, techniques of curing and conceptions of roles of the physicians, resulted in misunderstanding between himself, a physician and the client.

Marriott (1955) has conducted a study in a village named kishan garhi in Aligarh district of Uttar Pradesh. This study tries to explore the problems of introducing western medicine in Indian village community. Marriot has shown how the contracts and conflicts, between the roles assumed by the indigenous and western medicinal practitioners resulted in obstacles to the acceptability of western medicine.

Next, Hasan (1967) distinguishes between two types of social and natural factors that affect the health of any community's as factors that directly affect the health of the community

;a) Factors that directly affect the health of the community because certain customs, practices, belief's values and religious taboos etc, create an environment that helps in the spread or control of certain disease and b) Factors that indirectly affect the health of the community as they are related to the problem of medical care to the sick and the invalid. Nilanjan Khatua (2001): Carried out study on sickness healing and culture among certain Tribes. He classified illness into 4 categories 1. Illness by super natural power. 2. Illness due to disturbance of social system. 3. Illness due to angry of spirits and he felt rural's are the stronger believers in magico religious type of treatment

Talukdar (2002) has conducted a study on health culture of Karbis of Assam. He says diagnose and treatment of disease lies in the cognitive domain of culture of any particular community. However due to acculturation the health culture is keep changing now a days. Agarwal (2002) has conducted a study in a village of Rajasthan. He stated that health belief system of the rural is very deep rooted in their lives controlling certain rules of conduct of health behavior. Rao, (1986) In his study in Nainital District has observed that different communities in a village follows different indigenous medicine to cure the disease. Their health culture has been interwoven with their day to day life. Their health culture is influenced by their inherited social and cultural background.

Murdock (1980) and Shweder (1987) have found that explanation for illness in rural society will be basically bounded by psycho-social and spiritual rather than biological. Sometime in the rural societies people believe illness is due to the various social, cultural and psychological factors but surprisingly they will go for the western medicine for treatment!. Rural people strongly believe about cosmological forces causing various disease/illness for the variety of reasons. The cognitive domain of a patient will play a vital role in believing causes for health and illness and choosing a specific form of health care system in time to cure any health problems.

Swain (1994) has examined the perceptions of illness and diseases prevailing among the different social groups in rural India. He said social and cultural factors of the family like caste, class gender are the most vital factors in shaping the health culture and health behavior of the rural and tribal people. This is happening because illiteracy, isolation, remoteness, lack of unfaith on the modern medicine etc.

A study on reproductive health seeking behavior found that traditional beliefs and values also play an important role in determining health-seeking behaviour of women. This is more so

in the case of adolescent women who do not have any autonomy in decision making with regard to even their own health care. "It is not enough to educate adolescent women as they do not have any decision making authority. The target should be their parents and elders in the society who are required to be educated and made aware about these issues". Even adolescent women also suggested that the health programme should target more powerful decision-makers such as husbands and mothers-in-law in the household. Next, knowledge and awareness regarding source of health care is also a hindrance in seeking health care. Most of the adolescent women reported that they did not seek reproductive health services due to lack of money. Moreover, as daughters-in-law they get least priority in the household with regard to health care. Providers were also of the opinion that economic factor for adolescent women are a hindrance in seeking treatment. In addition, limited mobility of adolescent women and the need for male relatives or husband's accompaniment also delays seeking treatment (Sharma,2003).

Under nutrition and childhood mortality have become a serious problem among rural children. It is found that their social-cultural background, health, behavior and health culture dynamics plays a significant role as vital determinants of the health status of a particular community. Hence, under nutrition and childhood mortality are more common in rural areas. WHO report (1985) has found that 57% of death of under Five children in developing countries are accompanied by under-nutrition thereby low weight for their age. Anthropologists have revealed that the development of health culture of the rural environment should be examined as a sub cultural complex of the entire way of life. There are a number of forces percolated from the larger socio-economic environment and directed through the attributer of historical, social and political dimension to the development of the pattern of their health culture in the given rural settings. Under Five children need good nutritional diet which is scanty in many rural settings in the country and this causes mortality and morbidity among rural population.

Further, experts opined that poor health outcome of the rural community and their children need to be read within in the context of rapid urbanization, focusing poor health infrastructure, costly treatment etc. However, in a multicultural society rural childhood mortality in India cannot be analyzed in a contextual vacuum. Instead, they need to be looked at in the light of larger socio economic changes experienced by the rural community over the period of time. Till now various Governments have implemented many programmes to improve the

nutritional status of the pre-school children through various innovative schemes. Corers of money have been spent. Still the country experiences sever rural child mortality issue. Health experts opined that lack of good primary health care, perceived and personal risks, lack of awareness have lead in failing health improvements programmes. Also it is found that traditional health seeking behavior towards certain diseases severally hampering their health status. It is found that prevalence of respiratory tract infection, anemia, typhoid, and deficiency of vitamin A &B are more common and it might be due to their food habits. Poor household ecology, personal habits, cultural practices regarding delivery, childrearing and breast feeding also place a vital role.

As India strives towards becoming a more egalitarian society, health of marginal section of the society has become a significant issue and health education become serious factor in reaching its goal. Some noted developmental agencies have developed the concept of innovative Health Modernity' to be implemented in the rural areas in rural areas of Karnataka -India. Problems of accessibility, remoteness and poor transport system in rural areas are most common problems to be faced by the health workers in Karnataka. It is because of difficult terrain and sparsely distributed rural population in forests and hilly regions (Nanjunda,2009).. Next, lack of appropriate man power policy, inadequate funding mobilization, lack of government support, absence of proper and suitable approaches, lack of trained and committed staff also plays a vital role on the accomplishment of the NGOs interventions. Some time services will not be client friendly in terms of timing, cultural barriers, inhibiting utilization etc. Non involvement of rural people and weak monitoring and supervision systems also counts.

Certain studies have suggests that the lack of optimal utilization of health services by rural's may be due to a variety of reasons. Some services are inappropriately used, whereas others, such as preventive health programmes, are under-utilised due to lack of awareness. In addition, one of the main problem identified with rural's was communication difficulty to interact with external forces . Sociologists said what is required to improve the awareness about basic health concepts of rural's is, culturally appropriate health instructions, better and easily accessible medical services with a sympathetic and understanding attitude of the doctors and health staff.

It is expressed by the experts that the effects of health care interventions of various health schemes should not be limited to improvements of rural people's health status. Interventions should have a broader intention, such as empowerment of rural beneficiaries to get more control over health determinants, health behaviour and to find out their own solution/s for their health dilemma and the solidarity with vulnerable segments of that population. It really requires a holistic way of health development and management (Ratna, 2009; Shah, 2010). Overall this suggests that with improvement in socio-economic status, various aspects of service quality assume importance for the optimal utilization of services and the policy makers need to be sensitive about it. It has been observed that though the Indian government has made efforts to set up a vast network of healthcare centers in deep interior regions of rural areas, their importance is declining due to neglect of service quality (Bhandari, 2006).

Cultural Competence in Rural Health Care

Cultural competence in health care describes a health care system that is accessible and respects the beliefs, attitudes and cultural life-styles of professionals and of patients. It is a sad truth that, the quality of rural health care received varies greatly depending on class, caste and socioeconomic group, or place of residence (especially if it is rural). Cultural awareness and synthesis of learning are on-going requirements for the delivery of optimum patient-centered rural health care. In the social environment and health logic model access to "health promotion, disease and injury prevention, and health care" serves as an intermediate indicator along a pathway linking resources in the social environment to health outcomes. An important component of access to care for culturally diverse rural populations is the cultural competence of healthcare systems". This is integral to healthcare quality, because the goal of culturally competent care is to assure the provision of appropriate services and reduce the incidence of medical errors resulting from misunderstandings caused by differences in language or culture. Cultural competence has potential for improving the efficiency of care by reducing unnecessary diagnostic testing or inappropriate use of services. Providing culturally competent services has the potential to improve health outcomes, increase the efficiency of clinical and support staff, and result in greater client satisfaction with services especially in rural areas. Workforce diversity programs go beyond hiring practices to include organizational strategies for identifying barriers that prevent employees from fully participating and achieving success. Achieving diversity at all

levels of the healthcare organization can influence the way the organization serves the needs of clients of various cultural and linguistic backgrounds (Laurie M. Anderson,2003).

In summary, the literature reveals promising trends in outcomes-related research that should be further explored. Effective cultural based interventions appear to affect health services utilization, satisfaction, and increases in knowledge, although subsequent impacts on provider or patient behavior and/or health outcomes were not explored. Some studies that measured outcomes for specific interventions revealed contradictory and inconclusive results, due to significant variations in definitions, study design or approach. Their findings cannot be easily generalized, further supporting the need for additional research. Clearly, the results of this literature search demonstrate an opportunity to further build an evidence base linking cultural competent interventions to specific impacts on rural's health behaviour

6.SOCIOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCES OF THE PRESENT STUDY

The explicit study of health in sociology (Medical Sociology) has a long history. Sociologists have long pointed out the implication of prevailing socio-economic conditions on the health seeking behavior of the rural folk. It is well known fact that culture is inseparable from the human behavior. Generally Sociologist/Antropologist's views health culture as an attribute of the social life of human beings. Medicine and society are the centrally focused concepts in medical Sociology/medical Anthropology. Since cultural is an integrated functional unit of a society, Sociologists/Antropologist's tries to find out how health problem is interlocked with the local culture issues. Sociologists who are working on health development programmes have produced adequate theories and research methodologies dealing with the processes of change in the health seeking behavior of the rural people that are vitally important in framing new theories and health policies.

Further, it can be noted that due to the influence of changing socio-economic pattern, political issues, awareness, particular health culture will get framed and reframe continuously.To reveal the psycho-sociological compliant of health culture first we need to take into account the overall culture of the community. It is known fact that certain cultural practices it-self creates certain health disorders. Certain cultural practices of the community will get either by the diffusion or may be the own local innovation. Social science in general and Sociology in particular play a vital role in understanding of both qualitative and quantitative changes in the

various domains of health culture of the rural people. This empirical study will come out with new and unique findings and contributes to the theoretical understanding prevalent in the concerned domains of the subject to fill the research gaps.

An in-depth sociological study has acquired a greater relevance to the present day health problem emphasizing on how community evaluates the risks in different adopted and acquired health behaviors and the therapies preferred (including medical pluralism) and why some rural people have been reluctant to use the modern medicines. It is also most important to know an extent to which how people are responding to the different health policies and programmes of both Government and NGOs. Differences in the changing attitude and outlooks regarding various health /illness disorders in rural societies are very important for any medical sociologists.

6.6 NEED FOR THE CURRENT STUDY

Today the majority of rural people are suffering from various communicable and non communicable diseases. It is stated there is a positive correlation between the health status of the rural people and their social, economical and cultural health practises. Over the last few decades various Indian governments have developed few policies to achieve long term goals to provide a comprehensive health care programme for the rural people, and have increasingly emphasized the more immediate need to provide essential basic primary health care and scientific management of rural the rural population's traditional system.

The first one is sociology and medicine which focuses the contribution of sociological knowledge to the diagnosis and treatment options to cure disease/illness. Next, sociology of medicine focusing on the sociological study of the medical profession. An in-depth study of health culture of any rural folk will help in understanding the complete knowledge of etiology, onset of health, disease, healing etc.

As far as an organic linkage with the rural health is concerned, there is no basic service for a comprehensive health intervention attempt to understand the rural health culture as a sub culture complex in developing a model of culturally suited health care delivery system especially for the rural people of the country. Very little work, however, has entailed an in-depth analytical study of comparative emic perspectives of different factors influencing rural people's health behavior in Karnataka-India. This current research has built on recent social science efforts to contribute to filling that gap in the present understanding of impacts of various changing internal

and external factors influencing the existing health culture and in shaping health seeking behavior of rural people in the selected villages of Karnataka. Further, this study will help in the long term improvement of the health behavior of the targeted population and research findings will certainly helpful in developing a culturally compatible and acceptable developmental intervention strategy at the grass root level for both the Government and NGOs.

6.c Outcome of the Study

1.This study has revealed how health seeking behavior of rural's is governing by various socio cultural factors in a multi cultural society and how it has been changing due to various external interventions (Govt/NGO/media etc);

2. This study has given solid theoretical background to frame cultural and geographical specific models for the effective health interventions and it may be a guide to the other agencies;

3. A bunch of recommendations has been given to both Govt. and NGOs regarding improvement of the interventions and will form a basis for necessary reorientation to the project staff in line with the established recommendations and agreed changes for future action;

4. This findings has been produced with analysis of the qualitative and quantitative data generated during the course of the study with standerized parameters. These parameters can be used as a guide to carry out similer kind of studies in other part of the country;

5.The study will also facilitate to develop some information and analysis on theoretical understanding and practical implications of various health interventions for rural communities in the country.

6.d Implications for National Policy/interests

1 This study would help in the long term improvements in health conditions of the rurals and research findings will certainly help in developing culturally compatible and acceptable health management intervention strategies at the grass root level for both Government and NGOs;

2.This study will come out with successful developmental models of studied NGOs and can be

implemented in other part of the country so that we can archive sustainable rural development;

4.This study will provide fresh data to the Government and other agencies for the speedy implementation of various socio economic programmes;

7.Major Findings of the Study

In the context of rural settings a number of factors play their role in health seeking behaviour, including people's beliefs regarding the origin and cause of illness; economic status, gender bias in health care, advice lend by family elders, relatives friends or educated folk, educational status of the patient and his parents ignorance, superstitious and so on. Thus, one can say that health-seeking behavior in rural settings is completely governed by cultural values, beliefs and traditions, and changes in the social status it counts a lot still. It is encase of various external agencies. Contrary to changes in health seeking behavior patterns of the rural people one also notices tremendous changes, which have occurred with respect to philosophy, knowledge, and practices of indigenous systems such as Ayurveda, Homeopathy, etc. It becomes important to work on problems of rural health because it differs from a particular area to another area owing to their geographical location, historical background and the processes of social change. For this, there is a need for proper understanding of sociological insight of health care and its dynamics specific to time and place so that relevant health programmes can he made and implemented.

There is a greater need for undertaking a village -specific study of the status and role of rural's which alone can throw up data that will make planning for their welfare more meaningful and effective. Our study found that social and cultural factors, along with decision making processes and advice lend by family and village elders, relatives and friends etc play a vital and important role in rural cultures to seek medical help within the context of medical pluralism including ritual healing, witchcraft and sorcery and so on. It includes both magic-religious and mechanic and chemical procedure studies conducted on practice regarding therapeutic knowledge in rural society have shown that an impressive array of practice that demonstrate empirical therapeutic knowledge including bone setting, inoculation etc. Our study also explored that cultural factors or criteria, symptoms and situations where disease is defined as illness by those participating in the healing process, which seek to layer or restore their patients health.

Further, it is learned that ethno-medical therapies are not employed simply in rural settings. Therapeutic process or medical practice is often fused with magio-religious activities. Thus even when mechanical or chemical therapy is employed, magico –religious elements may also be essential part of the prescription, or the treatment may be regarded as incomplete without the attention of mystical factors involved in the etiology of the illness.

Further, this study has found that the proximity of illness is a strategic social style for the perpetuation of the effective social order. Concept about wellbeing and ill being has been located in respondents' cultural understanding of different health practices'. Village people felt Social relationships are the most vital in the smooth maintenance of the social order including health and illness. We found in this study that 'diagnosing and healing are having the most vital role in the cultural interpretation of the illness ideology'. This study found that illness ideology of the rural respondents is embedded with social, cultural, historical, philosophical context of the community and Illness concept goes beyond the individual body and medical diagnose

It was noted during the study that though rural spend significant amount of money and time, their level of health education is tremendously poor. Due to their lack of knowledge, they visit traditional healers and ill-qualified medical practitioners. These practitioners take full benefit of the chance and exploit the poor and uneducated. Another ground for their not utilizing the (primary health centers) PHCs is the apathetic attitude of the providers towards these people. It is also due the rash and careless behavior of the staff. It is found that the rural women do not pay any notice to problems during pregnancy, and often neglect the treatment of gynecological problems. An additional issue is the very high incidence of RTIs like white discharge, gonorrhea and others among the studied samples. It was felt during the study that some type of mental illness is found among these rural's.

The correlation between health and beliefs have a large influence over the behavior choices that can result in improved health. While accepting medical "pluralism" as a historical reality, as an intrinsic value inherent in rural medical system, and as an ideal or desired goal that any multicultural society ought to achieve. It holds that while documenting or dealing with the "coexistence" of varied medical traditions and practices, we must not ignore or underplay issues of power, domination and hegemony and must locate our work in a larger historical, social and political context of rural multi cultural society. In light of the growing global networking of

“traditional”, “complementary” and “alternative” health systems on the one hand and the hegemonic and homogenizing role and presence of multilateral organizations in shaping national health policies on the other, such insights from history become extraordinarily important. Health education sometime may get fail in in-depth understanding of existing cultural meanings which indigenous people associated with health behavior. Health education programmes must be based on sacred values so as to make them culturally acceptable, An in-depth study of indigenous medicine from an emic prospective will help in through understanding the cultural symbols and meanings and their integration with the culture. The findings of this study will also help in clear understanding the most vital reasons for the resistance encountered or refusal to accept different medical system including modern medicine.

It is found that rural’s living in the different set of village adopts more or less similar methods of health seeking behavior. Though non-natives people (migrants) living in the villages and a few developed natives are adopting modern methods of health seeking, people living in the natives region resort to indigenous methods out of compulsions like poverty and ignorance about modern methods of medicine. Though a majority of them realize the ineffectiveness of faith healing, they adopt it as the final remedy for the reasons given earlier. However, some rural’s who have been uncovered to the outside world, refuse *to* rely on these methods through a greater part of them still follow it hence new policy on rural and tribal health needs to consider all these factors and should be framed with the the consultation of concerned population. It is found that majority of rural’s does not aware of any health rights and more study is required to answer how economic situation can be improved by using commercialization of indigenous healing technique and medicinal plants.

However, it was noted in this study that despite the socio-economic background of the rural’s, their attitude towards health and health facilities was just fairly infavor of modern medicine. Sizeable respondents were of the opinion that there was a difference in the present day health seeking behavior as compared to that of their ancestors. This practice is of concern, since inappropriate use of allopathic drugs may ultimately lead to the disastrous development of resistance to drugs. Proper health education is necessary to prevent this. This study suggests that the lack of optimal utilisation of health services by rurals may be due to a variety of reasons. Some services are inappropriately used, whereas others, such as preventive health programmes,

are under-utilised Practical difficulties experienced by rural's may be another reasons for under-utilisation. Also one of the main reasons identified was communication difficulty faced by many NGOs due to language problem. What is needed to improve the awareness about basic health needs of rurals is, proper health education, better medical services with a sympathetic and understanding attitude of the doctor and health staff. Rural's share a perspective on health and wellness that is also reflected in their cultures. Our suggestion is to establish a traditional medicine initiative to foster formal relationships between local service units and traditional healers, so that cultural values and beliefs, as well as traditional healing practices, are respected and affirmed by the local Govt. as an integral component of the healing process.

Also it is found that the hierarchical principle of high and low caste is not only with the social groups. It existed with that of medical pluralism also. The caste class clasrificate is norurady contract with the " Medical pluralism hierarchy" (Gupta,1990). Wealthy respondents' will go for modern medicine dominating on traditional medicinal system. Govt. will also support modern health care sidelining the value of traditional medicines. The broad variety of halting culture co-existed along side of traditional medicine in rural societies now. This were established that in some case traditional healer will follow certain diaqustic technique available in the modern medicine. In is hampering due to the part chugging socio-economic culture of the rural respondents' de to globalization and other powerful external agencies. In urban setting respondents' are showing interest in ayurveda and homeopathy than allopathic. Lack of publicity, under striding variation of pluralism medical system found in the various rural setting has because a vital drawback in implementing culture specific health care programme to the rural respondents'. Late but never govt and NGOs should think in this direction

It is found that negotiations among various types of ' medical co-existing therapeutic system and between patients and practitioners in term of former of legitmain'' in vital in the long run of any ISM. May effort can be seen in India to incorporate ISM in to the main stream. It is only can be possible through the usage of various social institutions. Drug industry is also plays vital role in creating more network among them server for on time availability of various types of indigenous medicine. Also this medicine has psychological and spiritual dimension. Issues in also focused on the efficacy standardized of medicine and safety. Because some types of traditional medicines are not safe to use in the its original forms, more over it is also found that number in trained Practioners are also growing with respect to ISM in India. Today letter than

rural respondents' urban respondents' showing interest in using various forms of Indian medicines.

8.CHAPTARIZATIONS

1. Introduction
2. Conceptual-clarity, Objectives, Research Design and Methodology
3. Health Culture, Health Behavior and Medical Pluralism in the Rural Context
4. Review of Literature
5. Sociology of Health and Illness
6. Rural Health Scenario in India
7. Result and Discussions
8. Conclusion and Summary
9. Major Findings and Policy Suggestions
10. Bibliography
11. Appendix

Thesis Structure and Reading Guidelines

A. **Introductory chapter** briefly explains the importance of the topic, and gives very detailed introduction and background

B. The **Second chapter** objectives, methodology, conceptual framework of the study, limitations of the study

C. The **Third chapter** deals about solid background on health culture, health behavior and medical pluralism in the rural context.

D. The **Fourth chapter** provides a review of the literature related to the study. The related studies are classified into four groups namely,

1. Studies relating to health status, consisting of studies related to the socio economic and other factors that determine the health status of rural people,
2. Studies relating to health culture, health behavior
3. Studies relating to medical pluralism, consisting of different systems of medicine
4. Other related health studies focusing rural health issues.

E. **Fifth chapter** discusses about theoretical perspectives on sociology of health illness. It provides an over view about various health belief models, approaches and theories including lexicalizations and other factors affecting on rural health culture

F. The **Sixth chapter is on** health Scenario in Karnataka state -India

G. The **Seventh chapter** deals about result and discussion. It is the major chapter of the study and has been divided into four sub chapters;

i): Social, Economic, Demographic factors of the respondents

(II) General Health status, practice of the respondents

(III) Health concept, culture, medical pluralism and health behavior towards various illness/diseases

V) Relationship between various social determinants and the health behavior

vi) Perception of traditional healers, community and the Allopathic doctors

H. The **Eight chapter** gives a picture of summary and conclusion and

I. The **Ninth chapter deals** about major findings and policy suggestion

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Signature of the Scholar

